

TEACHING DISCOURSE ANALYSIS AND VOCABULARY

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ABSTRACT: *This article briefly explains the procedure of the carried out lesson devoted to explanation of the correlation of Discourse Analysis and vocabulary. The lesson plan and procedure aims both at giving the key notions related to vocabulary in terms of analyzing the discourse as well as attempting to exemplify the procedure of conducting the lesson on the given topic.*

Keywords: *discourse analysis, vocabulary, word meaning, idioms, collocations, chunks, lexical set, word family, false friends, cognates.*

INTRODUCTION

The present article aims at showing the procedure of carrying out the lesson on topic “Discourse Analysis and Vocabulary”. It will show the particular lesson plan of the conducted lesson together with the key and most important notions and concepts related to topic as well as the results of the lesson. The detailed procedure of the lesson was genuinely created and applied at the lesson to ensure the aim of it meets all the needs and requirements of the particular module. It shows the strategies, methods and techniques used by the Teacher.

Taking into account that the lesson is the mixture of supplying the key theoretical concepts related to topic and attempt to practice those crucial concepts at the same time, it was difficult to present the full-scale scenario as it was originally conducted. So, this article is an overall frame based on which the particular subject of the practice of language aspects teaching can be delivered to the Students¹. Moreover, we tried to introduce some modern and not trivial techniques and methods to teaching such a complicated module of the curriculum.

The procedure given in the present article is based on the real lesson which was recently carried out together with the results of it, conclusions as well as suggestions relevant to the teaching of the particular module to the students of the second course

¹ Abdugofurova, M. S., & Yugay, E. V. (2022). COMPETENCY-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD AND ITS INFLUENCE ON EDUCATION SYSTEM. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY, 1(4), 115–118. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/conf/article/view/421>

specializing at the English language teaching¹. The information and results given herein can be of some practical help not only to the teachers and students of this realm but also to the learners of the language as the information classified and given herein is the grounds for their further language learning.

The Procedure of conducted Lesson

Name of the subject: The practice of language aspects teaching / Discourse Analysis Module

Name of the topic: Discourse Analysis and Vocabulary

Length of the lesson: 80 minutes

Number of Students: 16

Level: Intermediate

Type of the lesson: Practical lesson (PPT based, group discussion, team work)

Lesson outline:

1. Introduction of the topic;
2. Setting lesson objectives and new concepts; explaining the lesson procedure;
3. Presenting the new materials and concepts based on Power Point presentation;
4. Team work – playing idioms game;
5. Assigning Homework.

Objectives of the lesson:

1. To introduce new concepts related to the topic;
2. To practice identifying idioms based on pictures.

Activities type:

- Group work – discussion, QA period;
- Team work – idioms game, handouts with exercises, puzzle solving;

Lesson Procedure:

Part 1. At the beginning of the lesson Teacher explains the lesson procedure and order of the lesson. After it, the Teacher introduces the new topic to the class based on the PPT presentation. At the same time the Teacher checks Students' comprehension by asking related questions.

The key points given by the Teacher which were presented to the Students with the help of the overhead projector and Power Point Presentation are given below:

Vocabulary (hereinafter referred to as the Lexis) refers to individual words or sets of words, for example: *tree, get up, first of all, all's well that ends well*, i.e. units of

¹ B. Paltridge (2006). Discourse Analysis. Continuum. 29, 53

vocabulary which have a specific meaning¹. But *What kinds of meaning can words have?*

There are the following types of meaning we need to identify:

DENOTATIVE MEANING = basic meaning, is the meaning that describes the thing or idea behind the vocabulary item, e.g. a TREE is a large plant with a wooden trunk, branches and leaves.

FIGURATIVE MEANING = metaphorical, extended meaning, is **imaginative** meaning and refers to what a lexeme means in a particular sense, e.g. 'the TREE of life', 'a family TREE'

CONNOTATIONAL MEANING refers to the emotional content of lexemes and is often a matter of culture. It may be positive or negative:

CF: "dense" vs. "dumb as a tree"

CONTEXTUAL MEANING = situational meaning, is the meaning that a vocabulary item has in the context (situation) in which it is used,

e.g. 'We couldn't see the house because of the tall trees in front of it' we understand how tall the trees are partly from knowing the meaning of tall and partly from knowing how tall a house is, so the meaning of tall in this sentence is partly defined by the context.

There are also words that regularly **occur together**, such as **collocations, fixed expressions and idioms**.

Collocations are words that often occur together, such as *to take a holiday, heavy rain, arrive at, depend on*.

There are many words which collocate in a language, and the degree of collocation can vary.

CF: *watch out - watch a video - watch the postmen*.

Fixed expressions are expressions which can't be changed, such as *to tell you the truth, new born, it's up to you*.

Idioms are a kind of fixed expression as they can't be changed, but their meaning is usually different from the combination of the meaning of the individual words they contain (e.g. *to be under the weather, to have green fingers, once in a blue moon*).

Collocations, fixed expressions and idioms are all different kinds of **chunks**. 'Chunks' refers to language that occurs in (semi-)fixed units and that **we usually learn as one piece**. *Have a good trip, I'd like to..., how about..., my name's ...*, are further examples of chunks.

They may be part of the same **lexical set** - groups of words that belong to the same topic area, e.g. *family, furniture, food*.

¹ M.Spratt, A. Pulverness, M. Williams (2011). The TKT Course. Cambridge University Press. 16-20

They may also belong to the same **word family** - words that come through affixation from the same base word, e.g. *real*, *really*, *realistic*, *unreal*.

False friends, homophones, homonyms and varieties of English are other ways in which words can relate to one another.

False friends (or COGNATES) are words which have the same or a similar form in two languages but a different meaning.

CF: *Embarazado* means “*pregnant*” in Spanish.

BUT: It **does not mean** *embarrassed*, though it **looks as if** it does to an English speaker!

Part 2. After having introduced all the key notions and concepts related to the topic, the Teacher asks some concept checking questions to make sure the Students clearly understood the topic. In order to consolidate and practice on the information recently given Teacher involves Students in practical part of the lesson which also includes some stages:

Stage 1. Practicing and consolidating the presented material:

Task 1:

What does each of these sets of words have in common?

Are they synonyms, antonyms, lexical sets, compounds, idioms, collocations, word families, homophones, words with prefixes or words with suffixes?

A) table, chair, sofa, bed, bookcase, chest of drawers, desk

B) old-young, bright-dark, loud-quiet, fast-slow, first-last, long-short

C) to be over the moon, all roads lead to Rome, pay through the nose

D) a straight road, a brilliant idea, hard work, no problem, extremely grateful

E) neat-tidy, precisely-exactly, to doubt-to question, nobody-no one

F) microwave, toothbrush, paper clip, lampshade, bottle top

G) illness, badly, useless, doubtful, affordable, ability, practical

H) imperfect, rewrite, unable, illiterate, incorrect, ultramodern

I) learn, learner, learning, learned

J) bear-bare, flour-flower, sea-see, which-witch, right-write

Students involve in group discussion aimed at consolidating the given material as well as applying the gained knowledge into practice.

Stage 2. Teacher shows the Students some pictures by means of which they need to find out the idiom. The most challenging part is that the picture shows the idiom by its direct meaning. Based on the picture the Students are to identify the given idiom's form as well as to try to identify the meaning of the idiom depicted. Students practice at analyzing the words' types of meaning and involve in discussion related to clarifying its actual meaning.

The list of idioms presented in pictures are as follows: - *to bite the bullet*; - *to be all ears*; - *a piece of cake*; - *to burn the candle at both ends*; - *to let the cat out of the bag*; - *to pull someone's leg*.

After having implemented the particular technique, the Teacher explains that the next part of the lesson is being conducted in form of competition between the groups, thus making the Students more involved in the lesson.

Stage 3. In order to divide the Students into 3 groups the Teacher uses the following method: each student is being distributed with an envelope. Each envelope contains a piece of colored paper. There are 3 colors used so students will have to quickly be split into 3 subgroups/teams. After they split and make up a team, Teacher instructs them on the following activity. It will be the same as they have recently practiced. But from now on they are going to compete with each other. The Teacher asks the Students to work in team and moreover to hold a team discussion before submitting any answers.

The task for this stage is the same: to guess the idiom based on the picture related to it. Students are asked to put numbers on the sheet of paper from 1 to 10. The Teacher shows the pictures one after the other allowing the Students to hold a discussion and agree on the answers.

The list of idioms given by the pictures:

1. To cut corners
2. To cost an arm and a leg
3. Cold feet
4. Break a leg
5. To spill the beans
6. It is raining cats and dogs
7. To be under the weather
8. To hit the books
9. In a nutshell
10. To bite off more than you can chew

After all the pictures are shown and Students have written their answers, the Teacher shows the pictures again and asks the answers from the team allowing them to explain and justify their answers. As a results, the Teacher keeps record of the correct answers and identifies the winning team.

Stage 4. The teacher brings to the attention of the students that the envelopes with cut pieces of colored paper were not given only with the purpose of dividing the group. They have specific shape so when you gather them, they will make up a puzzle pieces

complete¹. Besides of being the pieces of puzzle, there is something written at the back side of them. Now, the Students are involved in solving the puzzle by bringing the pieces together. If they do everything correct, there is a quotation for each team. After completing the puzzle, each team is asked to recite the quotation and involve in discussion related to its meaning.

The quotation used for this activity are as follows:

1. “You can’t build a vocabulary without reading. You can’t meet friends if you ... stay at home by yourself all the time. In the same way, you can’t build up a vocabulary if you never meet any new words. And to meet them you must read. The more you read the better.” (Rudolf Flesch)

2. “As vocabulary is reduced, so are the number of feelings you can express, the number of events you can describe, the number of the things you can identify! Not only understanding is limited, but also experience. Man grows by language. Whenever he limits language he retrogresses!” (Sheri S. Tepper)

3. “Your understanding of what you read and hear is, to a very large degree, determined by your vocabulary, so improve your vocabulary daily.” (Winston Churchill)

Final Stage: Teacher asks students to finalize the lesson by drawing some conclusions and sharing their feedback on the obtained information and activities they have recently involved in. As Home assignment, the Students were advised to practice more idioms and find pictures related to them in order to keep them in mind.

CONCLUSION

As it was already mentioned before, the subject of the practice of language aspects teaching is being quite challenging to the students of the second course. The topic was intentionally chosen for its difficultness being crucial and basic for the purpose of acquisition and understanding of the English language. As the key concepts and notions are being clearly and easily explained, it is true to state that the information provided in lesson procedure is of high value for language learners. Besides, the techniques and methods used and explained in detail can be easily adopted by all the English language teachers and not only those teaching particular module. The level of the information provided can be subject to change allowing this lesson to be modified based on the different abilities of the language learners.

¹ Shimchuk, A. O., & Yugay, E. V. (2022). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ИГР НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЛЯ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY, 1(4), 105–110. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/conf/article/view/419>

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